

Flavonoid constituents of *Euphorbia dracunculoides* Lam

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Euphorbia dracunculoides Lam. is a wild weed growing throughout India. The presence of a gluco-alkaloid and a phenolic compound from the stalks and leaves of the plant has been reported earlier¹. Recently Singh and Srivastava² isolated euphorbol, sucrose and a flavone glycoside from this plant. They however did not carry out any detailed work on the flavone glycoside.

The plant *E. dracunculoides* has been re-examined by us. The defatted powdered whole plant was extracted with ethanol. The residue left after removal of the solvent was extracted with water and phenolic glycoside part was then precipitated with saturated aqueous lead acetate solution. Decomposition of the lead salt with H₂S gave crude flavone glucosides which showed three very close spots in paper chromatography. It has not been possible to resolve the above mixture either by column or paper chromatography. The crude glycoside mixture was therefore hydrolysed with acid and the product on column chromatography yielded a yellow crystalline flavone, C₁₅H₁₀O₆ (M⁺ 286), m.p. 270-72° (decomp.); λ_{max}^{EtOH} 267, 317 (infl.) and 368 m μ , $\lambda_{max}^{EtOH-AlCl_3}$ 268, 305 (infl.), 345 (infl.) and 422 m μ . On treatment with ethereal diazomethane it furnished a tetramethyl ether (C₁₉H₁₈O₆, m.p. 165-66°) which was crystallised from methanol. The above flavone was identified as kaempferol by direct comparison (m.p., mixed m.p., and paper chromatography) with an authentic sample.

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1. N. Singh and A. Singh, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1959, 258.
2. A. Singh and S. N. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 420.